

USE OF AN ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SENSOR TO MONITOR DELAMINATION AND MOISTURE UPTAKE IN CFRP-REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) materials are being used increasingly to retrofit concrete bridges. Retrofits on beams, pier caps, and decks typically involve bonding of CFRP to concrete, and the integrity of the bond is crucial for success. Moisture and salt ingress into rehabilitated components have the potential to degrade the bond between CFRP and concrete due to continued corrosion within the concrete, delamination of the CFRP during freeze/thaw cycles, or thermodynamic weakening of interfacial chemical bonds. It is therefore important to develop a nondestructive evaluation method to monitor the integrity of the bond between CFRP and concrete in rehabilitated structures.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) sensors have recently been developed to monitor paint coatings and substrate corrosion and moisture degradation of metal-metal, metal-composite, and composite-composite adhesive joints. These sensors have also been used to inspect CFRP-reinforced concrete structures exposed to a variety of test conditions (salt fog, alternate immersion in fresh water, alternate immersion in salt water, 100% relative humidity, 50% relative humidity, elevated temperatures, and below-freezing temperatures). Other specimens were used to investigate the detection of delamination between the CFRP and the concrete using a modified wedge test configuration. The use of external electrodes attached to the CFRP surface, coupled with the embedded rebar, provided the best results. Equivalent circuit modeling was used to analyze the impedance spectra. Several circuit parameters, especially the capacitance and constant phase element (CPE) magnitude, correlated very well with both bonded area/delamination and moisture. Both parameters exhibit a linear relationship with delamination area. The capacitance also shows a linear relationship with moisture content while the CPE is more strongly dependent on moisture. The separate relationships between different circuit parameters and moisture or bonded area should allow these two material properties to be separately determined. The response of the sensors appears to be global in nature (for the relatively small laboratory specimens) so that a high density of sensors may not be needed to monitor critical areas of a large structure, such as a bridge. Differences in the response of the specimens subjected to the different exposure conditions were seen and explained based on the moisture uptake of the various specimens.

Coupled with a commercially available portable potentiostat, these measurements can be made in the field to facilitate inspection of concrete structures reinforced with CFRP, such as bridges.

Similar measurements on composite aerospace structures offer the potential for health monitoring of bonded repair and predictive assessment of other bonded or composite structures.

Keywords: Electrochemical impedance, moisture, delamination, adhesive bond, sensors

INTRODUCTION

The nation's civil infrastructure is aging and maintenance budgets are inadequate to replace all deteriorated structures. New construction and major repairs/refurbishment are being reduced or delayed so that existing

Figure 1. Left) A FRP reinforced support (from Ref. 4). Right) Applying a CFRP reinforcement to a concrete beam (from Ref. 3)

structures need to last longer than their design lifetimes. One of the most serious civil infrastructure problems is the deterioration of reinforced concrete (1). The cost of repairing or replacing deteriorated structures is estimated to be more than \$20 billion and to be increasing at \$500 million a year (2). The primary cause of this deterioration is the corrosion of steel reinforcing bars due to chlorides from deicing chemicals and seawater. During the winter months, many highway agencies use a large amount of salt-based deicing chemicals, usually sodium chloride. A large number of bridges have also been built in coastal areas and are exposed to seawater.

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) materials are being increasingly used for new construction or to retrofit bridges (Figure 1) (4-10). Examples of FRP applications in bridges include reinforcing steel or concrete beams for added strength or stiffness, wrapping concrete columns to restore/increase load capacity or to increase seismic resistance, or composite decks for increased loads and/or minimized repair time. Advantages of FRP construction/rehabilitation include light weight (increased live loads allowed), corrosion resistance, increased seismic tolerance, modular construction (greater quality assurance and less traffic disruption), and lower life costs. The lower life costs projections rely on the longer life of the structure compensating for the generally higher initial costs. Although claims of 100-year durability are made for FRP structures, the lack of long-term experience is a negative factor in increased use. A review by the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) reported that although the criticality of moisture/solution effects was high (5 on a 5-point scale) for external FRP reinforcement of beams, slabs, and columns, the availability of data was very poor (11). Despite the reluctance of many conservative engineers to use FRPs because of lack of experience, a recent marketing survey projected that use of FRPs in construction will increase by 525% globally and by 750% in North America from 2000 to 2010 (12).

The integrity of the bond between the FRP and the concrete or steel structure is crucial for success, especially for beam and slab configurations. Similarly, the integrity of composite-composite bonds, many of which are internal to the structure, is crucial for performance of FRP decks. Moisture and salt ingress into rehabilitated components has the potential to degrade the bond due to continued corrosion within the concrete or steel, delamination of the FRP during freeze/thaw cycles, or thermodynamic weakening of interfacial chemical bonds. It is therefore

important to develop a nondestructive evaluation method to monitor the integrity of the bond between FRP and concrete or steel in rehabilitated structures.

This paper outlines the development of *in-situ* sensors to detect moisture ingress into a CFRP-reinforced concrete structure and delamination between the CFRP and the concrete. This sensor has previously been used to detect the early stages of coating degradation, moisture uptake, and substrate corrosion of painted structures (13-16). It is also capable of detecting moisture ingress into a composite and an adhesive joint and bonded area (17-19). The sensors are based on the established laboratory technique of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and when coupled with a portable potentiostat, are suitable for both laboratory and field inspection.

EXPERIMENTAL

A series of short (1 ft or 305 mm) CFRP-reinforced concrete specimens and longer (2 ft or 610 mm) CFRP-reinforced concrete specimens were prepared. Chloride (11 kg/m^3 or 18.6 lb/yd^3) was added to the concrete to promote degradation and corrosion. The concrete was allowed to cure for 4 weeks. Internal sensors were mounted into a groove cut on the surface of the concrete. A section of release film was placed at one end of the concrete to prevent bonding with the CFRP. Carbon fiber fabric was then bonded to the block with an epoxy resin system formulated for concrete applications. External tape sensors were then mounted on the CFRP above the interfacial internal sensors.

EIS measurements involve applying a small ac voltage (10 mV) between the two electrodes and sweeping the frequency (typically from 0.1 Hz to 10^4 Hz) using a potentiostat. The current (magnitude and phase) that is induced by the voltage is measured at each frequency and the impedance spectrum is then calculated. EIS measurements were taken initially (before any condi-

tioning/exposure) and at various times during exposure using a potentiostat with different combinations of sensors: $E1I1$, $E2I2$, ..., $RE1$, $RE2$, ..., and $RI1$, $RI2$, ... where E^* is an external sensor, I^* is an internal sensor, and R is the rebar.

The impedance spectra were modeled using the circuit shown in Figure 2, which has previously proven very successful in modeling EIS data for bonded metals and composites (17). The circuit modeled most of the data well, but approximated others by not modeling all the spectral features. Other circuits with more parameters were tried in a few cases. They could provide improved fits but convergence of the circuit parameters could be an issue. (There is no one circuit suitable for a given data set; an infinite number of circuits can model any data.) Despite the approximation of the circuit of Figure 2, several of the parameters correlated very well with exposure time or bonded area (see below) so this circuit is considered suitable for the data analysis.

The concrete specimens were exposed to several conditions to promote degradation or to act as controls. The exposure conditions for the short specimens included:

- $T=50^{\circ}\text{C}$ (120°F)
- $T=-18^{\circ}\text{C}$ (0°F)
- $T=23^{\circ}\text{C}$ (74°F), 50% RH
- $T=34^{\circ}\text{C}$ (93°F), 100% RH
- Salt fog (ASTM B117)
- Alternate immersion (2 hr wet, 10 hr dry) in fresh water

Figure 2. Equivalent circuit used for modeling impedance spectra.

- Alternate immersion (2 hr wet, 10 hr dry) in salt water

The first three conditions represented different types of control exposures while the remaining four represent different accelerated testing. Three specimens were exposed to each condition. The data were individually modeled and the resulting circuit parameters were averaged over the three specimens. The data were very reproducible, especially for the rebar/external sensors on which the analysis was focused. In most cases, the three spectra for a given specimen overlaid on top of each other so that they could not be distinguished.

The longer specimens were used in modified wedge tests, which are commonly used to evaluate bond durability of metal-metal bonds. Two different exposure conditions were used:

Dry – The wedge was progressively driven into the specimen and EIS measurements taken with the crack between each pair of electrodes, i.e., 2-3, 3-4, ..., and a final reading with the crack beyond electrode #6.

Pre-exposed – The specimen was immersed in salt water (2 hr wet, 10 hr dry) for four weeks and the wedge driving procedure described above was performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of Moisture

The effects of moisture are best observed with data from the short specimens, as they had no change in bonded area over the exposure period and any changes in the data resulted from moisture intrusion. The external electrode/rebar pairs provided the best data and the following discussion is concentrated on these measurements.

Examples of the impedance spectra, in the Bode representations are given in Figure 3. Clear and regular changes in the spectra are seen for all representations. Equations 1 and 2 illustrate the dependence of capacitance C on both bonded or electrode area A and moisture M , based on a parallel plate configuration:

$$C = \epsilon\epsilon_0 A/d \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

and

$$C = \epsilon_0(\epsilon_{cc} + M(\epsilon_w - \epsilon_{cc}))A/d \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, ϵ , ϵ_{cc} , and ϵ_w are the dielectric constants of the specimen, the dry composite/concrete structure (~ 6), and water (80) (20-22), respectively, and d is the distance between electrodes. In Equation 2, the total specimen dielectric constant is assumed to be the volume average of the dielectric constants of the composite, concrete, and water. Because

Figure 3. Impedance spectra for specimens undergoing alternate immersion in salt water. Electrodes were the external electrode and the rebar. The legend gives the exposure time in days. Left: Bode magnitude plot; Right: Bode phase angle plot.

the dielectric constant of the composite (~ 4) is close to that of the concrete and the thickness of the composite is small compared to that of the concrete, the composite's contribution has been combined with that of the concrete.

For specimens for which the bonded area does not change, Equation 2 can be rewritten as

$$M = (C / C_i - 1) / (\epsilon_w / \epsilon_{cc} - 1)$$

Equation 3

where C_i is the dry capacitance.

The capacitances of the CFRP-reinforced concrete specimens are compared for the different exposure conditions in Figure 4. Although this figure is somewhat complex, it provides a wealth of information:

- The capacitance of the specimens exposed to 50% relative humidity (RH) at room temperature or at -18°C is constant, indicating that little or no additional moisture

Figure 4. Capacitance of the CFRP-reinforced concrete specimens as a function of exposure time for different exposure conditions.

Figure 5. Capacitance of the salt water-exposed specimens as a function of time. All nine combinations of electrodes are shown. This figure illustrates the low variability between the different electrodes of the same pairing. The legend indicates the electrodes: *e*-external, *i*-internal, and *r*-rebar.

was absorbed.

- The capacitance of the T=50°C specimens decreases, indicating that specimens are losing moisture and/or that the epoxy is undergoing additional cure at the elevated temperature. (The initial cure was at room temperature.)
- The capacitances of the specimens exposed to moisture increase, indicating moisture uptake.

Other points to be made from the external/rebar capacitances shown in Figure 4 are that there was no difference between the bonded (electrodes #2 and #3) and delaminated (electrodes #1) regions of the specimens and that the external/rebar capacitances are much larger than the external/internal and internal/rebar capacitances (Figure 5). These two findings indicate that the carbon fibers in the CFRP are serving to increase the area of the electrodes so that the entire specimen (for these laboratory-sized specimens) is being interrogated. The measurements thus have a “global” aspect and the measurement is not simply located at the electrode. In contrast, the much smaller capacitance of the other measurements (and the greater variability) suggests that the internal electrode is limiting the detection area.

The moisture levels can be calculated from the capacitance using Equation 3 (Figure 6). Moisture levels range from 0.6% to 2% after 40-45 days of exposure. This would include water within the pores as well as water incorporated into the concrete material.

Other equivalent circuit parameters also track with exposure time to the different conditions. The most notable is the CPE value (Figure 7). Upon moisture absorp-

Figure 6. Moisture levels after approximately 40 days.

tion, the CPE decreases by two to three orders of magnitude, a much larger change than the factor of two exhibited by the capacitance. Again, the 50% RH specimens and the T=-18°C specimens show no change over time.

Figure 7. CPE values as a function of exposure time for the different conditions.

The decrease in the moisture-exposed specimens is rapid initially and begins to level off for most specimens by the end of the exposure period. A comparison of the trends of

CPE and capacitance (or calculated moisture) suggests that the decrease in CPE with moisture is not linear, but that constant exposure to moisture (salt fog or humidity) results in a more rapid decrease in CPE than cyclic exposures. This suggests a percolation effect for moisture in the pores of the concrete.

The other circuit parameters including alpha (the phase exponent of the CPE) and R_{cpe} , also track with exposure time and moisture, but with some variability or anomalies (Figure 8). Alpha begins at about 0.8, which is near that of a capacitor ($\alpha=1$). For two of the control specimens, it changes very little. For all of the moisture-exposed specimens, it drops to about 0.5, the rate of decrease depends on the exposure conditions with the same grouping as the CPE magnitude (100% RH + salt fog and fresh water + salt water). At $\alpha=0.5$, the CPE becomes a Warburg constant, which is often used to describe a diffusion-limited reaction.

The resistive components also show trends of decreasing with moisture uptake. Current investigations include determining which parameters will most reliably indicate moisture and which will distinguish between moisture and delamination effects.

Effects of Delaminations

The effects of bonded area are best observed with the wedge test specimens in which the wedge was progressively driven between the composite and concrete to propagate the crack and, hence, reduce the bonded area. Two different sets of specimens were tested in this manner – one under ambient conditions that was nominally dry and one following salt water immersion for 28 days. Of the three combinations of electrode (external/internal, external/rebar, and internal/rebar), the external/rebar pairs again gave the most consistent and reliable results with the internal/rebar pair surprisingly also offering information on the bond state. Examples of the impedance spectra in the Bode representations are given in Figure 9. The changes are more subtle than those seen with moisture uptake (Figure 3), but have a different character, suggesting that moisture and bonded area effects may be distinguishable.

Figure 8. Alpha (exponent of CPE and, R_{cpe} , as a function of exposure time for the different conditions.

Figure 9. Impedance spectra for dry wedge test specimens. Electrodes were the external electrode and the rebar. The legend gives the bonded length in mm. Left: Bode magnitude plot; Right: Bode phase angle plot.

Figure 10. Left) Capacitance as a function of external electrode number for the dry wedge test specimens. The legend and the short vertical bars show the position of the crack tip. Right) Capacitance averaged over all electrode positions as a function of delamination size for both the wet and dry wedge test specimens.

With equivalent circuit analysis, the circuit parameters of the dry and wet wedge test specimen sets show a significant dependence on bonded area although the moisture absorbed by the second set provides a different correlation with bonded area. Figure 10 helps to define the effective area determining the capacitance. The left-hand graph shows that for a given crack tip position (i.e., bonded area), the capacitance is independent of whether or not the external electrode is in the bonded area or the delaminated area, yet there is a strong dependence overall on the bonded area of the specimen. When the average capacitance is plotted versus delamination, there is a linear relationship passing through 100% delamination (no bonded area). These findings show that the effective area is the entire 600x150 mm (2 ft x 6 in.) of the specimen. This large area is consistent with the much larger capacitance of the external electrode/rebar measurements compared to those using the external/internal electrode pair and the internal electrode/rebar pair. The carbon fibers in the CFRP provide enough conductivity so that the entire CFRP (in these laboratory scale specimens) acts as an electrode to couple with the rebar, which extends the length of the specimen. In contrast, measurements involving the internal electrodes have a much smaller effective electrode area and, hence, capacitance. The extent to which the carbon fibers in the CFRP extend the inspection area of the sensors will need to be established using larger specimens.

The capacitance of the wet wedge test specimen exhibits much higher capacitance, as expected. Nonetheless, the dependence with bonded area remains linear. In this case, there is residual capacitance if the relationship is extrapolated to zero bonded area (100% delamination). This capacitance is an indication of the presence of moisture in the specimen.

The remaining circuit parameters also exhibit a strong dependence on bonded area as shown in Figure 11. The CPE magnitude varies inversely with bonded area for both the dry and wet speci-

Figure 11. Circuit parameters as a function of delamination size for the external electrode/rebar pair. Dashed lines and open symbols correspond to the dry specimens. Solid lines and solid symbols correspond to the wet specimens. Clockwise from upper left: CPE, alpha, and R_{cpe} .

specimens although the dry and wet values are shifted by a factor of about 200. In contrast, the CPE phase angle, alpha, is independent of bonded area, but it does exhibit a dependence on moisture as shown in Figure 8. This dependence on moisture level and independence of bonded area may prove key in separating out the effects of these two properties on impedance spectra and the different circuit parameters.

The resistive elements also exhibit inverse relationships with bonded area for both wet and dry conditions as exemplified by R_{cpe} in the figure. For R_{cpe} , the change with moisture is a factor of about 60 compared to a change with bonded area of 2.5-4.0. Other resistances exhibit other proportionalities. It is expected that the different dependencies of the different circuit parameters

with moisture and bonded area will enable these material characteristics to be independently determined for an arbitrary structure in the field.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings can be summarized as follows:

The EIS sensors can be used on CFRP-reinforced concrete structures to determine both moisture content and detect delamination.

Simple single-frequency measurements may be suitable for moisture detection, but equivalent circuit modeling is needed to analyze data for delamination and more reliable moisture determination.

Impedance spectra from the external electrode/rebar pair provide the best correlation to moisture and bonded area.

These measurements are global in nature (at least up to the size of our largest laboratory specimens) so that a high density of sensors is not needed.

Using a commercially available portable potentiostat, measurements can be taken in the field.

EIS offers potential as a non-destructive method to interrogate the structural integrity of the bond between CFRP to concrete used in civil transportation structures.

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